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CLIMATE CHANGE, POLLUTION, AND BIODIVERSITY LOSS: KEY ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES OF THE MODERN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

The 21st century has brought several environmental problems to our planet. Greenhouse effect, abnormal weather conditions, floods, landslides, drought, lack of drinking and irrigation water, and environmental pollution. It is obvious that a single country, no matter how strong its economy, cannot fight these problems independently. Naturally, the UN, the EU, and its relevant infrastructures are working intensively to combat these problems. However, life has shown that regional states should also cooperate to solve these pressing problems. As you know, our region also faces these problems, the Aral Sea disaster, the shallowing of the vital Syr Darya and Amu Darya rivers, the melting of local mountain glaciers, the use of fossil fuels for energy production, etc. In cooperation with Central Asian countries to solve the above-mentioned problems, Manas Forum 2024 can be the platform where joint action programs for Turkic countries can be worked out.

Political aspect of cooperation of the Organization of Turkic States on the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As it is well known in the global world, the countries of the Turkic states are influenced by such large economies of the world as the USA, Russia, China, the EU, Japan, and the UK. Companies of those countries are the main investors in the economy of the countries of the Turkic states. In addition, these countries are the main donors in the field of socio-economic programs of the countries of the Turkic states. Therefore, based on this, the Republic of Uzbekistan, headed by President Mirziyoyev Sh.M., is pursuing a policy of equidistance concerning those large states. As it is known from astronomy, a separate planet, even of small size, will exist if it is located between large planets, because the gravity between large planets does not allow it to be absorbed by

another large planet. Therefore, Uzbekistan maintains good economic and strategic relations with all of the above countries. As a result, investments in the economy of Uzbekistan come from all large economies, including India, Saudi Arabia, and South Korea.

Renewable energy sources in the countries of the Turkic states (on the example of Uzbekistan).

Along with the Turkic states, Uzbekistan is striving to switch to renewable energy sources. Currently, Uzbekistan is one of the leaders in renewable energy investment in Central Asia. Along with the World Bank and the EBRD, investments come from China, Russia, the EU, and South Korea. As you know, in 2021, Uzbekistan made a voluntary commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere per unit of GDP by 35 percent by 2030 compared to 2010. Uzbekistan plans to produce 40 percent of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030. At the same time, it cooperates with ACWA Power of Saudi Arabia, as well as with several companies from Western European countries for reaching those targets. As you know, one of the main problems of renewable energy for households is accumulation of those energy, because of the high cost of batteries. Since Uzbekistan purchases a huge number of electric cars and other battery-powered vehicles, then as disposal of used batteries, can be used as a battery by households for renewable energy.

Cooperation in the educational system of the Turkic states.

In my opinion, the system of school and higher education in the Turkic states needs to be unified. As it is known, the developed countries have liberal education system and it is practiced in schools, colleges and in universities. It cannot be said that they are perfect, but the main thing is that this liberalism makes it possible to quickly adapt training programs to the demands of the time. The emergence of artificial intelligence and the development of robotics technology significantly change the structure of the training program and its timing. New occupations appear, and some existing ones disappear. Many universities hire successful businessmen or top managers of large corporations as heads of the Business school faculty. We should follow those tendencies. In my opinion, it is necessary to introduce a unified system of academic degrees in the Turkic states. Unfortunately, in some Turkic states, both PhD and Doctor of Science degrees are valid. Naturally, they need to be unified and only a PhD should be left. It is clear that these degrees are awarded by universities in developed countries. It is too early to practice this method in the Turkic states. Perhaps the Turkic countries create their own common scientific journals and joint academic councils for awarding academic degrees. Otherwise, the qualifications of scientists in these countries may decline due to nepotism and corruption. It is necessary to establish close ties between homogeneous universities and individual faculties of the Turkic

countries. For example, professors can use their sabbatical period in some universities of other Turkic countries. It is necessary to organize joint grants and student and schoolchildren exchanges between the countries. The languages of the peoples of all the Turkic countries should be taught in schools in the Turkic countries. It would be reasonable to introduce a single alphabet for all the countries of the Turkic states, although there is no consensus on this yet. To organize tourist trips for schoolchildren and students to the countries of the Turkic states. This strengthens the social, ethical, and cultural relations between the populations of these countries. It is desirable to organize a visa-free regime between the Turkic states.

Economic cooperation between the countries of the Turkic states.

Until now, these countries have been quite successfully cooperating in the field of economics and finance. But I propose to introduce, similar to the European Union, a symbolic common currency unit such as ECU (European currency unit) for mutual financial settlements. The future will show whether a single currency is needed to be introduced in the Turkic states. In light of the water shortage and weather anomalies, the question of the economic security of each country of the Turkic states is valuable. Therefore, it is possible to create a common structure of the Turkic states for economic security. Perhaps they will create a common customs union similar to the European Union and a common international development bank. It is highly desirable to establish a common Chamber of Commerce and Industry that coordinates production and helps to attract investments into the industry. It is very useful to establish an Exim bank in each country of the Turkic states. This will significantly help the country's import and export operations. The economies of the Central Asian countries need a large volume of investment for processing agricultural products and for civil infrastructure. Turkey's experience in exporting agricultural products and processing them may be helpful in this.

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